

Next Steps Miro Board

From your perspective, what SMD-level governance and standards work needs to be prioritized first?	From your perspective, what do you think are the main takeaways of the workshop?	From your perspective, what will be the challenges to an SMD-level governance initiative?
<p>To support interdisciplinary science, agreeing on (standardizing) nomenclature is a good start.</p> <p>A replicated infrastructure for user support (like Earthdata Forum) could be useful. I would not make a single forum across all of SMD – too broad and hard for users to find what's of interest to them.</p> <p>Ongoing discussions (like this workshop) are very valuable for helping us learn from each other (within and across divisions).</p> <p>Defining Minimal FAIR requirements across and within fields</p> <p>What is the guidance on accepting non-NASA data in a NASA SMD repository?</p> <p>Defining the metadata fields to require across all NASA SMD (e.g. refining what fields are required for SDE) establishing minimal implementation guidance for those fields (e.g. using SPDX identifiers for licenses) without getting into science-specific items</p> <p>Consistent and easy ways to measure compliance with SPD-41a and FAIR - if we can measure compliance and identify our gaps, we will be more likely to achieve the goals</p> <p>How best to define DOIs (what is a "dataset"? what happens with dynamic datasets? etc.)</p> <p>standardized dictionary at a high level that lets us all understand the same conceptions and have fruitful discussions</p> <p>the kind of interoperability that is being talked about requires funding of low-level, boring infrastructure, and this takes a while to implement and longer to have an effect, so there needs to be long-term thinking about this</p> <p>a funded project that explicitly called for proposals to leverage a successful capability from one SMD area to apply it in 2 or more other divisions would give people a chance to find low hanging fruit</p> <p>Reviewers of such a project need custom training to avoid existing problems in similar cross-science efforts. support for efforts to increase alignment across the repositories, such as working out what a levels of service approach looks like in each division, working together to understand how to write proper answers for the desirable characteristics, etc.</p> <p>centralizing archival support for research data with low transparency, including model outputs, likely through a Zenodo-like community with some management at the division level (e.g. science specific items). Data repositories should be allowed to choose what they (and the contributors) wish to apply a higher level of service to.</p> <p>establishing and supporting a community of practice for data repository software</p>	<p>hosting and serving data on the cloud is more expensive than we thought. The services have to be redesigned to work with s3, data egress is a huge cost factor, and it takes people of higher skill levels (and pay) to maintain cloud infrastructure rather than sys admins for on-premise.</p> <p>I have several follow-up discussions for collaboration opportunities.</p> <p>We need to think more carefully about what needs to be in "Creative Destruction"</p> <p>loosely applying the idea of levels of service could work across the divisions - key word here is LOOSELY. More discussion needed.</p> <p>Researcher-contributed data needs a categorization system that is NASA SMD-wide and better support. Most repositories aren't set up or even interested in supporting it, but the community desperately needs proper services for them. Questions remain about how long these data should be preserved for, possibly influenced by usage and 5-star ratings over time.</p> <p>Need more people across the science divisions focusing on topics like the ones discussed here, and they need to talk to each other more easily somehow.</p> <p>It's clear that for FAIR compliance, more discussion is needed. Also, better definition of categories needs to be put together so everyone is on the same lexicon.</p> <p>We all seem to spend a lot of time trying to interpret policy and doing it differently - e.g. what makes for a compliant backup/restoration solution? What makes for a compliant "independent peer review"? etc.</p> <p>Encouraged by statements of overlapping needs to a define and implement FAIR</p> <p>As there is much to do, we will have to work together to improve efficiency and effectiveness.</p> <p>each of the divisions is actually doing a good job adapting their data repositories to the new requirements in SPD-41a</p> <p>Need a more coordinated and supported effort for aligning terms across NASA sciences. Should focus on general terms first (e.g. definition of a dataset and NASA-specific controlled vocabularies, such as for NASA missions).</p> <p>There should be more SMD-wide workshops like this! The divisions are all doing similar activities and can provide great perspectives and ideas for each other. Don't need to reinvent the wheel each time.</p> <p>we have more in common than our differences</p> <p>There's a lot going on and expertise that I'd like to have a forum for information exchange</p> <p>Discourse forum (e.g. like what Hello has with Helionauts; https://helionauts.org/)?</p> <p>the Earth Science Working Groups seem to be an effective way to focus a community on relevant topics for a few years; find ways to fund and stand up a suite of these kinds of groups in other divisions</p> <p>Each directorate's archives are at different maturity levels, and it may be helpful if more developed areas can not only take the lead but also help the other directorates catch up.</p> <p>I learned a lot of things to take back to my main domain (software in Helio). There's actually a lot of commonality in the types of discussion, challenges, etc. happening between s/w and data</p>	<p>Only generic items should be governed at the SMD-level. Any metadata or data component or characteristic that is specific to a science should remain governed by the divisions and repositories.</p> <p>Potential areas where SMD-level governance appears useful are the requirements and methods for Sci-X, SDE, a NASA Zenodo-ish community, and possibly a software search interface.</p> <p>Finding the time and resources to achieve these goals will be a challenge.</p> <p>We are constrained by the need to remain compatible with the rest of the astro community, which is more important for our users than SMD</p> <p>many data system changes don't focus enough on the workflows of real scientists; we need to make changes that have an immediate impact on improving science efficiency;</p> <p>People are very passionate about what they do.</p> <p>Dealing with the legacy of historical practice.</p> <p>Too many competing priorities.</p> <p>We've never done it that way before.</p> <p>At best, we might be able to get to one size fits many. HQ, in particular, has some tendencies towards edicts that have unintended consequences. Guidance will be useful. Requirements, not so much.</p> <p>On the implementation side, the difference make it difficult to have one approach</p> <p>There is a high risk of trying things top-down from HQ and having each division have to shoehorn things to a non-useful scheme.</p> <p>Governing well requires some domain expertise, without that good governance is difficult</p> <p>Hard to find persons with cross-science expertise</p> <p>Different SMDs have different domain-specific needs. That needs to be taken into consideration with any governance. Multi-level governance will help that. But also, a bit of flexibility will need to be coded into governance to allow for varying needs/specifications within each domain.</p> <p>there are some science areas that really don't make sense to connect, so it should be OK for those to be not unified into a single analysis system</p>
<p>Please provide initial feedback on the workshop itself including format, content and schedule.</p> <p>There were complaints about the ecocycle activity in person. The post-it notes were flying away and they were hard to read. Would have been better to have it completely online using Miro.</p> <p>The discussion groups for the ecocycle activity were too large for everyone to participate.</p> <p>Would like to see this workshop be done in collaboration with a new workshop focused on software for data repositories. Could make it a week with two days for each and overlap the two in the middle, maybe with poster sessions and networking on that day? Would be a great addition to add a place for such a community of practice.</p> <p>Outstanding. I don't have suggestions for improvement (which some may find shocking :-))</p> <p>Loved, loved, loved the ecocycle activity - I learned so much both about others and it also forced me to look introspectively at what we are doing</p> <p>Small, but I appreciated that in-person name tags showed the SMD divisions as opposed to institutions!</p> <p>Good representation across the SMD spectrum of science and level of responsibility. (+1)</p> <p>Wasn't overly scheduled. Lots of room for formal and informal discussion. (+1)</p> <p>Would love to see things like the ecocycle discussions happen hybrid, all on the miro board. I think there was a missed opportunity for in-person and virtual attendees to have discussions</p> <p>The miro boards were too open - people were editing things in them before the instructions were fully explained.</p> <p>Little to no technical issues was very nice... kudos!</p> <p>Miro boards have a learning curve, but they are a fun & interactive way to communicate.</p> <p>The length of the sessions was nice (2:15) - long enough to cover more than one topic in that category, but not so long as to warrant a snack break in the middle.</p> <p>Would like to see one short (10 min) presentation from the group of repositories in each SMD on the first day, perhaps to answer a set of predetermined questions. Would help orient us to what is going on in other divisions.</p> <p>Great location / hosting institution support</p> <p>a room with the ability to have questions be heard online, timing was great and allowed for good conversations, some sessions more interesting and fruitful than others.</p> <p>Miro boards aren't needed for everything. Sometimes a google doc is fine.</p>	<p>Do you have ideas on interdisciplinary, scientific use cases that could be prototyped to help better understand interoperability needs? Please list your use cases here. It would be great to identify some use cases that work across multiple repositories and/or divisions.</p> <p>self-promoting comment: I presented a poster on a simple interoperability mechanism for data access that is working across divisions (called HAPI); I do think that uniform, low-level data access mechanisms could help enable cross-division use of both data and software tools, and HAPI is one working example that applies across Helio, Planetary, and could work in other divisions too</p> <p>most of the divisions have some kind of data or software-focused workshops - have some overlap meetings sometimes for people to cross-calibrate</p> <p>What does API support look like for imagery data across the relevant repositories? Is there an easy simply service we can adopt and add to existing services to increase data accessibility across the sciences? Similarly for time-series data, but that seems more approachable (e.g. HAPI). Could involve helio, astro, earth, and others.</p> <p>Predicting significant radiation exposure for astronauts in space - requires BPS and Helio data and software.</p> <p>collaborative work towards cloud-friendly data formats would be useful, particularly for larger data - helio and earth sci?</p> <p>Analyzing the sun as a model for other stars - requires solar physics and astrophysics data.</p> <p>Using LLMs and similar AI technology to draft interactive documentation</p> <p>Characterizing and predicting the effects of cosmic ray radiation on manned spaceflight - BPS and astro</p> <p>Understanding the effects of solar weather on other planets in our solar system and their effects on space missions, both with astronauts and unmanned- helio and planetary, also BPS</p> <p>Increasing our ability to model and subtract cloud cover in astro images in various wavelengths - astro and earth sci</p>	

Next Steps Miro Board

Need a better system to communicate the 'stop talking' message.				
We need to step away with tasks for the year				
If we do an activity next year where everyone participates, such as a group effort on the desirable characteristics and our answers, we will need more discussion time.				
Can hotel blocks be reserved at GSA rates, preferably including breakfast?				
Needed more time for the posters. Perhaps add an hour of poster time on the second evening? in the same area as a networking function?				
Never use voting on a Miro board for complex topics or when a lot of reading is needed to decide. Could instead give everyone 5 tiny squares they can put next to their favorite items without a strict time limit.				
Move the group picture to be on the second day so more can be there.				
Would have liked a networking hour somewhere, maybe the second night?				